

Best Practices

From stars to the Cosmic Web: Exploring 3D printing as a tool for inclusive astronomy communication

Amelia Ortiz-Gil¹, Vicent Martínez García¹, Emilio Terol¹, Alberto Fernández-Soto², Fernando Ballesteros¹, Siddhartha Gurung-Lopez¹, Enrique Pérez-Montero³, Julia Suso¹

¹Observatorio Astronómico - Universidad de Valencia, ²Instituto de Física de Cantabria, ³Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía

The use of physical 3D models in astronomy communication with the public has already been proven as an effective way to disseminate science, with the benefit of including the blind and visually impaired community. We present here a set of ten new models (such as Laniakea and Ho'oleilana) based on real data and created using an organic 3D design, which has made them more accurate while also making them attractive and inspiring. We tested the models with non-specialist audiences and with persons who are blind, who helped improve the final designs and highlighted their usefulness in astronomy communication. The models are available on the A Touch of the Universe website, and a collection of four educational activities has also been developed and submitted for publication in the AstroEDU repository following a peer-review process. This project demonstrates how 3D printing can foster inclusion and multisensory engagement in astronomy education and outreach.

Edited by
Nic Bonne

Reviewed by
Kimberly K. Arcand

Submitted 9 January 2026
Accepted 27 April 2026
Published 11 May 2026

Corresponding Author
Amelia Ortiz-Gil
amelia.ortiz@uv.es

Citation
Ortiz-Gil, A. (2026). From stars to the Cosmic Web: Exploring 3D printing as a tool for inclusive astronomy communication. *Communicating Astronomy with the Public Journal*, 20(1).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20037832>

1. Introduction

The representation of astronomical objects in 3D and the process of printing them physically is attracting interest from both the scientific and outreach communities because of the benefits that astronomical data in 3D printed form provide to both research and outreach activities ([Jaworek, 2015](#); [Arcand et al., 2017](#); [Ortiz-Gil, 2019a](#); [Arcand et al., 2020](#)). It is also an effective way to include blind and visually impaired (BVI) publics in outreach and education events, both formal and informal ([Pérez-Montero, 2019](#); [Arcand, 2019](#)).

In academia, 3D printing allows astronomers to better identify or find links between the different structures and details of the objects studied ([Madura, 2017](#)). They also help researchers share their science with colleagues and constitute a key tool for visually impaired specialised researchers and students ([Grice et al., 2015](#); [Arcand et al., 2020](#)).

In outreach, the benefits are very relevant too, as they help the public to understand the intricacies of the celestial

bodies in a more straightforward way ([Bonne et al., 2018](#)). Interacting with the models allows the public to relate more closely to the object, and in so doing, to learn and retain knowledge in a more meaningful way than by simply seeing an image ([Shams & Seitz, 2008](#)). Moreover, adding an extra sense helps involve and motivate the public ([Trotta, 2018](#)).

This tactile exploration of astronomical data also has the advantage of being more inclusive for a diverse range of publics, as it is more accessible than images to persons who are blind or visually impaired, complementing and even improving the experience provided by images that have some kind of embossment ([Bonne et al., 2018](#)).

In 2007, the Astronomical Observatory of the University of Valencia started the development of 3D models for the communication of astronomy with diverse publics, including BVI persons. We developed “The Sky in Your Hands” ([Ortiz-Gil et al., 2011](#)), a planetarium show for the BVI community based on a previous experience in Argentina by Sebastián Musso, which relies on a half-sphere with constellations engraved on it and a directional soundtrack with individual sounds associated with each celestial object. We leveraged the 7-channel sound system at the Hemisfèric theatre in Valencia, Spain, to project these particular sounds from the position in the dome where the objects were being projected. In this way, the BVI public could easily locate the relative positions of the celestial objects in the dome through sound.

Later, we produced a model of the Moon that showed its most prominent visual features in relief ([Ortiz-Gil, 2018a](#)). Again, because the model was also intended for the blind and visually impaired community, we did not build a detailed topographical representation but rather a tactile translation of the most prominent visual lunar features to convey, through touch, what people see when looking at our natural satellite.

In 2008, our team got funding from the International Astronomical Union’s Office of Astronomy for Development (OAD) and others to create an innovative tactile astronomical kit, which was sent to 30 communicators and teachers in underserved communities throughout the world. This was the starting point of our award-winning inclusive astronomy communication project “A Touch of the Universe” ([Ortiz-Gil, 2025a](#)), which was followed by the development of Mapelia, a software to easily transform 2D maps of various projections into 3D spheres with relief ([Ortiz-Gil & Burguet, 2018b](#)).

The relevance of 3D printed resources in astronomy communication was highlighted, for example, at the International Astronomical Union’s “Inspiring Stars” travelling exhibition ([D’Antonio et al., 2018](#)), which features 3D models created by several research groups around the world, including the planetary models of “A Touch of the Universe”. More recently, the Donostia International Physics Center (DIPC) has created the travelling exhibition “STROM - Inclusive Astronomy, a multisensory and inclusive journey through the Universe” ([Rodríguez, 2023](#)).

In 2022, we were awarded funding for a Proof of Concept project (ref. PDC2022-133930-I00)

to investigate how to develop 3D tactile models of new celestial objects to communicate the science and results of our research project on astronomical surveys. The grant was funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033, and the European Union's "NextGenerationEU/PRTR".

This project was carried out with the main goal of expanding our expertise in the development of 3D printable models of complex and somewhat unusual celestial objects. To the best of our knowledge, the majority of the objects chosen have not yet been modelled in this way. The project is also an exploration of how we can communicate with the public – including the blind and visually impaired – the science and results of our National Program research project "Scientific exploitation of the J-PAS and J-PLUS surveys: Large-scale structure, distant objects and stellar populations and star systems (JAVESTARS)".

Therefore, the three main objectives of the project were:

- To understand which physical 3D representations of the data relevant to our research project have more impact and are more suitable for outreach activities
- To research and establish a set of recommendations detailing how to translate the different kinds of data related to the research project (large-scale structure, individual galaxies, stars) into 3D models
- To create new models that have not yet been developed by other research groups

In this paper, we will present the main results of this "Proof of Concept". We will explain how we chose the models we were going to work with, the challenges in the design and how they were addressed, the feedback from the non-specialist audiences and the blind and visually impaired community, some educational activities which involve the models, where to find the files to print them out, and some final conclusions about this work.

2. Model selection

The first step was to decide which celestial objects were the most suitable to work with, according to the following criteria:

- a. scientific and educational interest
- b. complexity of the model
- c. relevance to the parent research project
- d. novelty, no similar 3D models had been produced before

Models developed following a geometric design are, in general, easier to create and schematic representations can be a good aid to start understanding a particular object (Musso, 2023). In this case, we explored a more complex organic design. Previous successful attempts are

found in some cases, like the ones in “3D Printing the X-Ray Universe” ([3D Printing the X-ray Universe, 2025](#)), but they are still few, especially for multi-object celestial bodies.

Organic design has some advantages over geometric design: it is more pleasant to view, it is better at creating emotional responses and allows us to reproduce complex astronomical data more faithfully. Therefore, we included in the project a 3D designer with a fine arts background.

The models we decided to work on were:

1. Be-type star (theoretical model)
2. Active galactic nucleus (theoretical model)
3. Galaxy NGC 2997 (based on real telescope data)
4. Milky Way galaxy (based on data from the Gaia satellite)
5. Milky Way with galactic halo around it (based on data from the Gaia satellite)
6. Milky Way, including the stellar stream formed by its collision with the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy (based on data from the Gaia satellite)
7. Local Group of Galaxies, where the Milky Way and its neighbours reside (based on real data)
8. Coma galaxy cluster (based on real data)
9. Ho'oleilana, a baryon acoustic oscillation (BAO) (based on real data)
10. Local Universe, including several superclusters of galaxies such as Laniakea, in which the Milky Way resides, and the structure of filaments and voids that characterise the cosmic web (based on real data)

We acquired a Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) printer to avoid using support structures during printing, especially for more complex models such as the Local Universe/Laniakea (see [Arcand et al., 2017](#)). SLS printers work by sintering (or fusing) powder material contained inside a cubic printing chamber. The laser gradually fuses the powder, while the unsintered powder remains in place, surrounding the printed parts and thereby supporting any overhangs in the printed object. Also, SLS printing makes it possible to print interlocking parts, moving elements, nested components and many other highly complex designs.

This is not the case with fuse deposition (FDM) printers because they create objects from bottom to top that need all their parts to be connected to the printing bed. If the print has overhangs or floating components, it is necessary to include support structures that need to be removed from the final product after printing, which can leave bumps behind. A similar reasoning applies to resin printers (SLA), but in this case, supports are always required, even if there are no floating components.

Nevertheless, during the project, we also had access to SLA and FDM printers and conducted

a small comparison among these three technologies to gather feedback on the quality of experience for our blind participants (see Table 1).

3. Methods

As we wanted the models to be scientifically accurate, we used real data whenever possible to ensure the results were reliable and useful for educational and dissemination purposes. To transform complex astronomical data into meaningful physical objects, we followed a procedure based on two pillars: structural heuristics for non-solid data and a systematic language of tactile textures. This approach seeks to achieve a form of tactile synesthesia, where the physical properties of the models closely reflect the astrophysical nature of the objects they represent.

The representation of “non-solid” elements – such as the cosmic web, dark matter, or diffuse gas – required specific design strategies to ensure both structural integrity and conceptual clarity. Filaments and scaffolds not only serve as physical supports for “floating” objects (like galaxies in a cluster) but also represent the underlying dark matter distribution.

For large-scale structures derived from point-cloud data, such as the Local Universe/Laniakea and Ho'oleilana, we applied an organic grouping strategy. Discrete data points were smoothed into cohesive volumetric forms, or “blobs”, that preserve the structure's global morphology while remaining robust and readable by touch. In cases where the data implied a central structure suspended within surrounding features—as in Ho'oleilana—it was necessary to introduce a hidden, fictitious support to make the physical model viable without altering its conceptual interpretation.

Furthermore, for objects with internal dynamics, such as the Be star, we employed mechanical encapsulation, printing independent nested spheres in a single process. This allowed users to explore, through touch, the differential rotation between the inner and outer regions of the star. The model also includes a spiral structure representing episodic mass loss, which progressively opens as the distance from the star increases.

Complementing these structural strategies, we implemented a systematic haptic coding system. This ensures that textures are not arbitrary but act as objective data carriers. Intangible components, such as gas clouds and dark matter filaments, are rendered with smooth and polished textures. This allows them to function as a tactile “background” or guide, facilitating movement between points of information without creating sensory clutter.

Massive red galaxies are represented with smooth surfaces, reflecting their nature as “relaxed” systems in virial equilibrium. In contrast, spiral and irregular galaxies feature rougher textures, physically representing active star formation and tidal disruptions.

For complex structures like spiral arms, we intentionally exaggerated the relief and texture.

This ensures morphological legibility, allowing the user to distinguish the spiral pattern from the inter-arm regions easily.

In cases where specific objects within a complex model need to be identified by name, we added embossed Braille labels or signs directly onto the model's surface. For instance, in the Local Universe/Laniakea model, superclusters are marked with their initials in Braille. This allows for autonomous identification by people who are blind or have low vision, reducing dependence on an oral guide and reinforcing the model's role as a self-contained educational tool. Ho'oleilana features embossed signs (cross, circle, square, etc.).

The consistent combination of structural solutions, tactile textures, and integrated labelling provides a powerful tool for inclusive communication. By establishing an objective and reusable tactile language, educators can perform "tactile pin-pointing" during outreach activities, using textures and labels as shared reference points. This approach facilitates faster and more intuitive identification of structures for both blind or low-vision participants and non-specialist audiences. Design heuristics have been summarised in [Table 1](#).

Data type/challenge	Design principle	Astronomical system(s)	Modeling method
Spatially suspended objects	Filamentary scaffolding	Globular clusters; galaxy groups and clusters (Local Group, Coma Cluster); Sagittarius stream	Objects embedded in filament networks representing dark matter halos, providing both physical support and conceptual context
Point-cloud 3D datasets	Organic grouping of point-cloud data	Large-scale structures (Local Universe/ Laniakea; Ho'oleilana)	Smoothing discrete point clouds into cohesive volumetric forms; cosmic web modelled as filaments following observed large-scale structure
Central floating structures	Fictitious structural support	Ho'oleilana	Introduction of a fictitious internal support to stabilise the central supercluster

Complex morphologies	Reinforcement of empty regions	Spiral galaxies (Milky Way; NGC 2997)	Inter-arm regions rendered as smooth continuous surfaces to ensure mechanical robustness, with spiral arms emphasised as higher-relief structures
Internal substructures and/or dynamics	Mechanical encapsulation	NGC 2997 nucleus, Be star	Nested spheres showing underlying structures (NGC 2997), or a free-rotating inner sphere, enabling tactile exploration of differential rotation (Be star)
Mass and energy ejection and/or accretion	Reinforcement of empty regions	Be star AGN	Spiral structure modelling circumstellar gas, with increasing opening angle as a function of distance
Incomplete 3D positional information	Reproduction of 2D visual data	Coma Cluster	Observed transverse galaxy distribution preserved; line-of-sight positions assigned using plausible radial distributions consistent with available data
Cross-cutting accessibility strategy	Tactile pin-pointing	All outreach models	Consistent use of textures and labels as tactile landmarks supporting guided and independent exploration

Systematic tactile language	Intangibility coding	Dark matter filaments; diffuse gas; cosmic web	Smooth, polished textures used for intangible components, functioning as a tactile background and navigational guide
	Morphological coding	Elliptical, spiral, and irregular galaxies	Smooth textures assigned to virialised systems; rough textures used for star-forming or dynamically active galaxies
	Exaggerated morphological details	Spiral arms; complex substructures	Selective exaggeration of relief and texture to ensure immediate tactile discrimination between structural components
	Integrated labeling	Local Universe/ Laniakea Ho'oleilana	Braille or sign inscriptions embedded directly on model surfaces to enable autonomous identification of key structures

Table 1: Summary of design principles.

The models in which the Milky Way is featured were made from the latest data available from ESA's Gaia satellite, which provides the most precise knowledge of the structure of our galaxy to date ([The best Milky Way Map, by Gaia, 2025](#)). For the Ho'oleilana and Local Universe/Laniakea models, we contacted their discoverers and used the 3D renderings they included in their publications ([Pomarède et al., 2017](#); [Tully et al., 2023](#)).

4. The final models

A total of ten 3D models were created within the scope of this project, ranging from individual stars to the large-scale structure of the Universe (see [Table 2](#)).

Be star	Active Galactic Nucleus (AGN)	NGC2997
The Milky Way	Milky Way with halo	Milky Way and the Sagittarius Dwarf stellar stream

Table 2: A total of ten 3D models have been developed in this work..

The models have been hand-painted: In addition to achieving a great aesthetic effect, colours also help identify individual elements more easily, especially in more complex, multi-object models like H'oleilana, the Local Universe/Laniakea, or the Local Group of galaxies.

5. The final models

To disseminate these models and facilitate their use in science communication and education, we have developed a series of activities suitable for different age ranges. These are:

- Citizens of Laniakea
- The Milky Way and friends

- Ho'oleilana: Murmurs of Awakening
- A Tactile Voyage to the Milky Way

5.1 Citizens of Laniakea. In this activity, students interact with a 3D tactile model that represents the Local Universe, featuring galaxy superclusters (including the one we live in, Laniakea), filaments, and voids. Through manual exploration and guided calculations, they discover how galaxies and dark matter are distributed across large scales, how gravity shapes the Universe, and how everything is in motion, including our own galaxy. It has been developed for students aged 10 to 18 years old.

5.2 The Milky Way and friends. This hands-on activity uses 3D-printed models of the Sagittarius Stellar Stream, the Local Group of galaxies, and generic spiral and elliptical galaxies to help students explore how galaxies interact, evolve, and form structures in space. Through tactile exploration, guided observation, and mathematical reasoning, students learn about the dynamics of the Milky Way's environment and the cosmic forces that shape it. The activity is addressed to students aged 10 to 18 years old.

5.3 Ho'oleilana: Murmurs of Awakening. The activity introduces students to the concept of baryon acoustic oscillations (BAOs), which are sound waves from the early Universe that left traces in the large-scale distribution of galaxies. Using the 3D tactile model of Ho'oleilana—an actual BAO structure discovered in the cosmic web—students explore how these ancient ripples shaped the Universe and how astronomers use them as a cosmic ruler to measure distances.

Students also identify galaxy clusters and superclusters in the model. They learn how BAOs formed from the interaction between gravity and pressure in the early Universe, and how their frozen patterns help scientists understand dark energy and the acceleration of the Universe's expansion.

The students also hold guided discussions and perform calculations with real data, using scientific notation. It has been created for students 16+ years old.

5.4 A Tactile Voyage to the Milky Way. This hands-on activity uses 3D printed models of the Milky Way and its halo to help students explore the structure, scale, and history of our galaxy. Through tactile exploration, guided observation, and mathematical reasoning, students gain a deeper understanding of where we live in the Universe and how astronomers study it. It has been developed for students aged 10 to 18 years old.

Because these activities rely on tactile elements, they can also be carried out by children who are blind or have low vision, helping foster their inclusion and raise their peers' awareness of exploring and learning through senses other than sight. They also show students that working in a diverse team fosters creativity in discussions and problem-solving ([Ortiz-Gil, 2019b](#);

[Alemany & Vermeulen, 2023](#)).

These activities have been submitted to AstroEDU ([AstroEDU, 2026](#)), the International Astronomical Union's platform for astronomical educational resources. Prior to publication in that repository, they will undergo a rigorous peer-review process. "Citizens of Laniakea" ([Ortiz-Gil, 2026a](#)) and "The Milky Way and friends" ([Ortiz-Gil, 2026b](#)) have already been published on the Attribution 4.0 International-licensed AstroEDU website.

The Spanish-language activities are also accessible on the website of the ACIERTAS educational project, under the resources section: "La Vía Láctea y sus amigas" ([Ortiz-Gil, 2025b](#)), "Un viaje táctil por la Vía Láctea" ([Ortiz-Gil, 2025c](#)), "Ciudadanos de Laniakea" ([Ortiz-Gil, 2025d](#)), "Ho'oleilana: Murmullos del Amanecer" ([Ortiz-Gil, 2025e](#)).

6. Resources at the "A Touch of the Universe" website

The 3D files resulting from this work have been incorporated into the collection of resources we already had for our tactile astronomy project "A Touch of the Universe" ([Ortiz-Gil, 2025a](#)) to make them freely available to everyone.

The website is multilingual (Valencian, Spanish, English and Italian). It is based on an accessible WordPress template, readable by screen readers, with sufficient contrast for people with low vision, and colours suitable for people with colour blindness. Clear fonts that improve readability for people with dyslexia have been used. The descriptions of the models include a version that is easy to read for people with cognitive disabilities (only in Valencian and Spanish).

There is an entry for each celestial body, including its scientific characteristics and a detailed description of the 3D model and how the actual data have been translated into a tactile experience.

The "Downloads" page links to the documentation folder of each model. The folder includes:

- The 3D file(s) ready for printing.
- A "Readme" PDF with the description of the model and the copyright (in Valencian, Spanish, English and Italian).
- An annotated PDF with a detailed description of the object and an image of the most relevant parts in the model tagged with labels (in Valencian, Spanish and English).

7. Discussion

In this work, we have explored how to transform 3D renderings of astronomical data (e.g., point

clouds, images, and 3D virtual renderings) into physical objects. The prototypes developed here have been designed based on real scientific data; whenever possible, the exceptions are the Be star and the active galactic nucleus, which are based on theoretical models.

The objects created range from extremely hot giant stars to galaxies, and the clusters they inhabit, from a fossilised sound wave formed very shortly after the Big Bang to a region of the Local Universe over 1 billion light-years wide.

In many instances, they help to visualise complex objects, such as the Local Group of Galaxies, which allows us to put the Milky Way in its nearby cosmic context, or the Local Universe model, which allows us to appreciate our environment on a much larger scale and how matter is not uniformly distributed but forms long filaments, leaving empty spaces between them.

As this work is intended merely as a proof-of-concept project, we did not design a full protocol for the testing stage. However, since one of our objectives is to use the models in outreach initiatives for blind and visually impaired audiences, we have tested successive versions of our models with the help of volunteer blind individuals, progressively adapting the designs based on their suggestions.

To include persons with visual impairments, we have sought clarity in the designs from a tactile perspective, avoiding excessive or confusing details while remaining faithful to the scientific data on which the models are based.

In particular, during the design process, we consulted with two blind individuals. The first is a professional astronomer who combines his professional knowledge with his blindness. The second test was performed in collaboration with a person who is blind and has had little exposure to astronomy beyond what she learned from textbooks. One of the most important inputs we obtained from them from the very beginning has been the imperative need for clarity in the designs from a tactile point of view, avoiding excessive and confusing details. We have tried in all cases to avoid “sensorial cluttering” in the models, which can include both the design itself and the excessive use of textures or tactile symbolism. This has to be combined with the global aim of remaining faithful to the scientific data on which the models are based. After several iterations with our analysts, they highlighted that these objects helped them clearly understand our explanations of each celestial body’s nature, appearance, and properties.

We have also used the models successfully with people without visual impairments, such as schoolchildren who have visited us at the Astronomical Observatory, physics students in lessons at the University of Valencia, and non-specialist audiences at three science fairs and astronomy festivals. Though we have not yet obtained formal statistical results about these experiences, the participants in all groups demonstrated a greater facility in understanding concepts – some as difficult as the scale of the large-scale structure of the Universe or stellar streams around a galaxy – and a larger degree of participation and interaction compared to activities in which an explanation was offered without the support of a solid object. This

result was noticed by the tutors of the different groups and the scientists and communicators responsible for the activities.

Finally, a copy of the Local Universe/Laniakea model was sent to one of its discoverers, Dr Daniel Pomarède, who is the author of the 3D visualisations on which we relied to build the printable model. His reaction was one of absolute enthusiasm, recognising the high quality of the solid 3D representation of the original data.

Several models have been used by one of our colleagues in a TV show called “La Via Verda”, where he had a fortnightly section about astronomy (Figure 1). The models were really helpful to explain where in the Universe we live and what Laniakea is, what active galaxies and pulsars look like or how galactic satellites interact with their parent galaxies. The addition of physical models of objects that are difficult to apprehend (even with the help of 3D renderings or artistic visualisations) was highly appreciated by the showrunners, who considered them a very positive extension for the explanations given.

Figure 1 Several 3D models from this project were used to illustrate explanations about different astronomy topics in the TV show “La Via Verda” on “À Punt” TV. Credi: Mathies Muñoz

Throughout the project, we had access to other types of 3D printers, so we were also able to experiment with different printing materials, not just the PA12 powder used by our SLS printer. Thus, some models were also made using filament deposition (FDM) and with resin (SLA). The result of the filament models is not ideal, as the subtle layers of the object’s construction are noticeable. But the combination of regular and glow-in-the-dark filaments allowed us, in some instances, to represent the luminous and dark components of some celestial bodies more meaningfully (see [Figure 2](#)).

Figure 2 This Milky Way model has been printed using two different filaments: a black one and a white glow-in-the-dark one. This allows users to see the luminous parts of the galaxy shining when the room lights are off.

As for other printing materials, testers with visual impairments preferred powder over resin because it is more pleasant to touch, or in their words, felt “as if it were velvet”, possibly because of the high porosity of the 3D printed material. See [Table 3](#) for a more detailed comparison between different printing technologies.

	SLS	SLA	FDM
Extra supports	Not necessary	Not necessary	Necessary for complex objects
Tactile output	Smooth porous surfaces	Smooth surfaces	Needs post-processing to smooth out the surfaces

Printing accuracy	Highly accurate	Highly accurate	The extrusion process can introduce inconsistencies
Price per printed item	High	Moderate	Low
A variety of available printing materials	Not many	Many	Many
Tactile feeling according to BVI users	Excellent	Very good	Good

Table 3: A qualitative comparison between different printing technologies. A quantitative comparison depends heavily on the specific printer model.

8. Conclusions

In this work, we have explored how to interpret astronomical data of different types (e.g., point clouds, images, 3D virtual renderings) into physical objects. It constitutes an important step forward in the use of 3D printing for astronomy and science outreach.

This project has successfully demonstrated that it is possible to make physical 3D models that are also accessible to visually impaired people, which communicate the richness and complexity of celestial bodies. We have created entirely new models, such as the Local Universe/Laniakea, Ho'oleilana, the Local Group, or the Coma Cluster. In all of these, we have used novel organic designs that allow us to represent the details of every object more faithfully and make them more interesting and attractive.

We have tried some strategies to overcome different problems, such as how to represent "suspended" bodies, and how to create solid objects from 3D virtual renderings of data. We followed a procedure based on structural heuristics for non-solid data and a systematic language of tactile textures. This approach seeks to achieve a form of tactile synesthesia, where the physical properties of the models closely reflect the astrophysical nature of the objects they represent, and opens the door to developing physical 3D models of other objects or even concepts from other scientific fields, not only astronomy.

Access to various types of 3D printers has allowed us to compare different technologies, especially taking into account the tactile sensitivity of visually impaired users. During the tests,

we found that models printed through selective laser sintering have a feel that offers a more pleasant experience compared to resin and filament models.

All 3D files can be downloaded from the “A Touch of the Universe” website. Educational activities related to this work will be published in the AstroEDU repository after peer review. The first versions of the activities are already available at ACIERTAS, although only in Spanish.

It has been shown that knowledge acquired by involving several senses at once is better understood and remembered for much longer than when simply reading or listening (Shams & Seitz, 2008). Our new models contribute directly to achieving this objective, first attracting the attention of students and the public, with their beauty and uniqueness, and then giving way to amazement for the scientific content represented in them.

The overall result of this work is a collection of new, extremely interesting, and useful models for teaching and disseminating astronomy that are also accessible to people with visual impairments. Therefore, contributing to the goal of achieving a full integration of the blind and vision-impaired community in science communication and education activities.

This work is paving the way for the effective use of 3D printing techniques in inclusive, multisensory astronomy communication and education. The lessons learned here will help us (and others) create better tactile resources and activities in the near future.

Acknowledgments *This work has been possible thanks to a Proof-of-concept project PDC2022-133930-I00, funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033, and the European Union’s «NextGenerationEU/PRTR». AOG, VM, FJB, AFS, SGL and ET acknowledge support from research project PID2019-109592GB-I00/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 from the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (MCIN)–Agencia Estatal de Investigación, research Project PID2023-149420NB-I00 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU, and the project of excellence PROMETEO CIPROM/2023/21 of the Conselleria de Educació, Universidades y Empleo (Generalitat Valenciana). The authors are indebted to Juan Fabregat, Andrés Moya and Daniel Pomarède for their helpful discussions about some of the models.*

References

3D Printing the X-ray Universe. (2025). *Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics*. <https://chandra.harvard.edu/deadstar/>

Aleman, L., & Vermeulen, F. (2023). Disability as a Source of Competitive Advantage. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/2023/07/disability-as-a-source-of-competitive-advantage>

Arcand, K., Watzke, M., DePasquale, J., Jubett, A., Edmonds, P., & DiVona, K. (2017). Bringing cosmic objects down to Earth: An overview of 3D modelling and printing in astronomy and astronomy communication. *Communicating Astronomy with the Public Journal*, 11(1), 14–20. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14974450>

Arcand, K., Jubett, A., Watzke, M., Price, S., Williamson, K., & Edmonds, P. (2019). Touching the stars: improving NASA 3D printed data sets with blind and visually impaired audiences. *JCOM*, 18(04), A01. <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.18040201>

Arcand, K. K., Price, S. R., & Watzke, M. (2020). Holding the Cosmos in Your Hand: Developing 3D Modeling and Printing Pipelines for Communications and Research. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2020.590295>

AstroEDU. (2026). *AstroEDU*. <https://astroedu.iau.org/>

Bonne, N. J., Gupta, J. A., Krawczyk, C. M., & Masters, K. (2018). Tactile Universe makes outreach feel good. *Astronomy & Geophysics*, 59(1), 1.30-1.33

D'Antonio, M. R., Canas, L., & Merced, W. D. (2018). Inspiring Stars – the IAU inclusive world exhibition. *Proceedings of the International Astronomical Union*, 13(S349), 470–473. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1743921319000620>

Grice, N., Christian, C., Nota, A., & Greenfield, P. (2015). 3D Printing Technology: A Unique Way of Making Hubble Space Telescope Images Accessible to Non-Visual Learners. *Journal of Blindness Innovation and Research*, 5(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.5241/5-66>

Jaworek, G. (2015). *Blind zu den Sternen: Mein Weg als Astronom*. Aquensis.

Madura, T. I. (2017). A Case Study in Astronomical 3D Printing: The Mysterious η Carinae. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 129(975).

Musso, S. (2023) AstroTES. <https://astrotes.org>

Ortiz-Gil, A., Blay, P., Gallego Calvente, A., Gomez Collado, M., Guirado, J., Lanzara, M., & Martinez Nuñez, S. (2011). Communicating astronomy to special needs audiences. *Communicating Astronomy with the Public Journal*, 5(1), 12–15. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14890616>

Ortiz-Gil, A. (2018a). 3D Tactile Moon. *EPSC Abstracts*, 12, EPSC2018-869, European Planetary Science Congress 2018.

Ortiz-Gil, A., & Burguet, J. (2018b). Mapelia and friends: create 3D models from maps. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 3(25), 660. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00660>

Ortiz-Gil, A. (2019a). Las impresoras 3D como herramientas científicas. *Encuentros multidisciplinares*, 61. http://www.encuentros-multidisciplinares.org/revista-61/amelia_ortiz_gil.pdf

Ortiz-Gil, A. (2019b). Diversity across astronomy can further our research. *Communicating Astronomy with the Public Journal*, 13(2), 7–10. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14977767>

Ortiz-Gil, A. (2025a) A Touch of the Universe. <https://astrokit.uv.es>

Ortiz-Gil, A. (2025b). *La Vía Láctea y sus amigas*. ACIERTAS. <https://aciertas.org/recurso/la-via-lactea-y-sus-amigas/>

Ortiz-Gil, A. (2025c). *Un viaje táctil por la Vía Láctea*. ACIERTAS. <https://aciertas.org/recurso/un-viaje-tactil-por-la-via-lactea/>

Ortiz-Gil, A. (2025d). *Ciudadanos de Laniakea*. ACIERTAS. <https://aciertas.org/recurso/ciudadanos-de-laniakea/>

Ortiz-Gil, A. (2025e). *Ho'oleilana: Murmullos del Amanecer*. ACIERTAS. <https://aciertas.org/recurso/hooleilana-murmillos-del-amanecer/>

Ortiz-Gil, A., Terol, E., Fernández-Soto, A. (2026a). *3D Universe: citizens of Laniakea*. AstroEDU. <https://astroedu.iau.org/en/activities/2604/3d-universe-citizens-of-laniakea/>

Ortiz-Gil, A., Terol, E., Fernández-Soto, A. (2026b). *3D Universe: the Milky Way and friends*. AstroEDU. <https://astroedu.iau.org/en/activities/2601/3d-universe-the-milky-way-and-friends/>

Pérez-Montero, E. (2019). Towards a more inclusive outreach. *Nat Astron*, 3, 114–115. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-019-0693-3>

Pomarède, D., Hoffman, Y., Courtois, H., & Tully, R.B. (2017). The Cosmic V-Web. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 845(1), 55. <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa7f78>

Rodríguez, V. (2023). *STROM - Inclusive Astronomy*. Donostia International Physics Center. <https://dipc.ehu.eus/en/science-society/strom-inclusive-astronomy>

Shams, L., & Seitz, A. R. (2008). Benefits of Multisensory Learning. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 12(11), 411–417.

The best Milky Way Map, by Gaia. (2025). ESA. https://www.esa.int/ESA_Multimedia/Images/2025/01/The_best_Milky_Way_map_by_Gaia_labelled

Trotta, R. (2018). The Hands-on Universe: Making sense of the Universe with all your senses. *Communicating Astronomy with the Public Journal*, 12(1), 20–25. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14977346>

Tully, R., Howlett, C., & Pomarède, D. (2023). Ho'oleilana: An Individual Baryon Acoustic Oscillation? *The Astrophysical Journal*, 954(2), 169. <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aceaf3>

